

SCALIBUR Platform Online User Manual and result of quality testing Deliverable 7.3

Submission Date: 22 July 2021

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

The SaaS paradigm caused a deep change in the methodologies and techniques used to build the software and opened to new possibilities and new markets.

The SCALIBUR Cloud Platform follows this new modern paradigm and embraces the new potentialities of this new business methodology. The platform will be accessible from any device over the Internet without requiring to install any proprietary software as it was in the past.

Evolving in this direction, the SCALIBUR Cloud Platform has been designed to fulfill the new requirements born from the new implementation methodology to ensure a high-quality level of the software. A layered structure has been defined to be scalable and adaptable to the different needs that can be raised throughout the execution of the project.

The Platform SCALIBUR SaaS version represents the core component of the SCALIBUR ecosystem. This version is delivered after months of work and represents the first tangible software outcome resulting from the research, planning and business activities of the consortium partners. Due to the complexity of the overall ecosystem, this version narrows down the functionalities to the most important ones and offers a usable environment for feedback, research, dissemination and future development modules.

The deliverable is presenting the main functionalities, screenshots from the available screens and a list of proposed features to be implemented in the following versions.

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